

CONSUMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS ORGANIC PRODUCTS IN INDIA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THE 24 MANTRA ORGANIC

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ABSTRACT

Lifestyle changes in terms of health are the most attention paid activity in the existing world by way of organic product consumption. India being the place for traditional farming, profound use of chemicals and pesticides for such farming led to the artificial ideas of farming which have been made by man. A sustainable way of living is a type of lifestyle that is being adopted by various people in the contemporary world which has increased the consumption of organic products. Demands for organic products are being hyperbolized to a greater extent due to the enhanced level of health benefits and awareness among consumers. Organic products are produced in an eco-friendly way which reaps the advantages that are expected by the consumers. The levels of consumer satisfaction are altered in the consumption of organic and conventional products besides suffering from their limitations. One of the popular organic food brands in India is 24 Mantra Organic which draws its special attention by way of the products produced by them. The present paper focuses on measuring the satisfaction level of consumers using products of the 24 Mantra Organic brand, especially during the times of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: *Consumer, Satisfaction, Organic Products, Lifestyle.*

INTRODUCTION

The production of organic food is aimed at the conservation of natural resources unlike traditional food production with less emphasis on the environment (Yadav & Pathak, 2016). It also aids in animal health and environmental welfare. Organic foods contain fewer synthetic fertilizers and pesticides and are free of hormones and antibiotics that contribute to public health (Health Harvard, 2015). The consumer needs an in-depth understanding to make decisions regarding organic food purchases and consumption due to its increased relevance. Although consumer purchases of organic food have been studied regularly (Hughner et al., 2007; Juhl et al., 2017; Kushwah et al., 2019; Rana & Paul, 2017). On reviewing the literature some gaps have been found. Individual decisions on the purchase of organic products depend on certain contextual factors out of which COVID-19 is one predominant factor.

COMPANY PROFILE

The journey of Sresta began in the backdrop of excessive and harmful usage of pesticides

In 1992, when our founder, Raj Seelam was working in an agricultural products company, he observed the alarming use of chemicals usage on farms and the deep impact it had on rural indebtedness. Investment in pesticides and synthetic fertilizers meant farmers had to borrow money, which in turn was affecting the very sustainability of the farmer's life and standard of living.

With a group of inspired colleagues, we set out on a lifelong journey of passion and commitment. We named our products 24 Mantra. Delving into the ancient Upanishads of India and sourcing from the Rig Veda, we drew upon the primary elements of nature. Tvam Bhumir Apo Analo Anilo Nabha – You alone are Earth, Water, Fire, Air & Ether is the blend of all basic elements that compose wholesome food.

Working for the greater good

Sresta has been taking small steps since 2004. With the focus on creating means of sustainability, we set about addressing two key areas - farmers and products.

For the farmers, we directed our efforts toward creating communities that are committed to the cause of organic farming and ensure sustainable livelihood and mutually beneficial relationships with the farmers.

For products, we adopted a unique farm-to-fork approach to ensure that the agricultural produce is 100% organic and that customers can trace the journey of all the products back to their fresh, natural source.

Standing tall, standing strong

The journey has been a challenging yet fruitful one. Today 60,000 farmers cultivate 3,00,000 acres across 15 states. And our goal is to expand this circle of sustainability by reaching 1 million farms.

Buying 24 Mantra from Sresta means you are a votary of the healthy, nutritious movement. Like our farmers and us, you have decided to keep the planet in a sustainable state. Reduce the harmful chemicals and pesticides, keep the air and water clean and of course, keep the soil alive.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organic food purchasing is a private sphere of pro-environmental behaviour. Like other pro-environmental behaviour, organic food purchasing involves doing something for the greater good (Hughner et al., 2007; Larson et al., 2015) and thus also offers benefits other than self-benefits (White et al., 2019). Researchers tried to interpret the factors that underly an individual's decision to purchase organic food products due to their given importance. Research on the determinants of organic food purchasing has accumulated during the last decade. To structure the obtainable data, this analysis develops an abstract model - galvanized by an analysis of shopper decision-making (Belk, 1975; Gifford & Brigit Nilsson, 2014; van Doorn & Verhoef, 2015; White et al., 2019; Yüksel, 2012). Consensus exists that the choice to get organic food is often seen as a social quandary (van Doorn & Verhoef, 2011). In other words, people weigh their interests like self-preservation (i.e., egoistic motives) against collective or "the wider good" interests like the protection of others (i.e., altruistic motives) when they decide to purchase organic food. Empirical works reveal that both motives influence individuals' purchase decisions regarding organic food (Kareklas et al., 2014; van Doorn & Verhoef, 2011).

METHODOLOGY

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the present study are set as below:

- To determine the demographic profile of sample respondents selected for the study about 24 Mantra Organic products during the COVID-19 pandemic.
- To determine the consumer satisfaction of selected sample respondents for the study towards 24 Mantra Organic during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Data Collection and Sampling Method

Data is collected through a well-structured questionnaire to analyse the level of consumer satisfaction towards 24 Mantra Organic products from 50 sample respondents as primary data during the COVID-19 period through google forms. The convenience sampling method has been adopted for the study.

DATA ANALYSIS

Factor 1. Age

Factor 1 determines the age of the sample respondents for which they have been categorized into five forms. 4 per cent of responses are received from the category of below 18 years, 58 per cent from 19 years to 30 years, 22 per cent of responses from 31 years to 45 years, 14 per cent of responses from 41 years to 60 years and 2 per cent responses from above 61 years.

Factor 2. Gender

Factor 2 determines the gender of the sample respondents for which they have been organized into two categories. 40 per cent of responses from female respondents and 60 per cent of responses from male respondents have been received for the study.

Factor 3. Educational Qualification

Factor 3 determines the educational qualification of the sample respondents for the study has been categorized into five types. 2 per cent of responses were received from SSC, 4 per cent of responses from Intermediate/ ITI/ Diploma, 32 per cent of responses from Graduates, 46 per cent from Post Graduates, 16 per cent from Doctoral degree holders.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Sample Respondents

Demographic Factor	Categorization	Frequency	Percentage %
Age	Below 18 years	2	4
	19 - 30 yrs	29	58
	31 - 45 yrs	11	22
	46 - 60 yrs	7	14
	Above 61 yrs	1	2
Gender	Female	20	40
	Male	30	60
Educational Qualification	10th/ SSC	1	2
	Intermediate/ ITI/ Diploma	2	4
	UG	16	32
	PG	23	46
	PhD	8	16
Occupation	Employed	32	64
	Un-employed	18	36
Type of Family	Nuclear family	40	80
	Joint-family	10	20
Family Income	Below 2.5 lacs	26	52
	2.5 - 5 lacs	11	22
	5 - 10 lacs	11	22
	10 - 20 lacs	1	2
	Above 20 lacs	1	2

Source: Primary Data

Factor 4. Occupation

Factor 4 determines the occupational status of the sample respondents for the study has been categorized into two. 64 per cent of responses were received from Employed and 36 per cent of responses from Un-employed respondents.

Factor 5. Type of Family

Factor 5 determines the type of family of the sample respondents for the study has been categorized into two types. 80 per cent of responses were received from nuclear families and 20 per cent from Joint-family respondents.

Factor 6. Family Income

Factor 6 determines the family income of the sample respondents for the study has been categorized into five groups. 52 per cent of responses were received from below 2.5 lacs, 22 per cent from 2.5 lacs to 5 lacs, 22 per cent from 5 lacs to 10 lacs, 2 per cent from 10 lacs to 20 lacs, and 2 per cent have been received from the above 20 lacs family income group.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Higher responses are received from the age group of 19 years to 30 years showing the awareness of consumers by various influential factors turning them around. Age plays an important role in understanding, analysing and interpreting their levels of satisfaction rather than getting influenced by factors like peer suggestions, advertisements, paper clippings, sample product feels and the like. Male respondents were proactively involved in analysing the satisfaction levels of 24 Mantra organic products by considering various factors like price, availability, quality and so on. Education plays a major role in the perceptions and ideology of consumers where higher responses have been received from the postgraduates. As a general principle deduction, employed people responded at higher rates exhibiting their factors of influence. Nuclear families can actualise the importance of any aspect of their lives since they are restricted to a limited size. Family income and type of family are interdependent because of their personal preferences out of which nuclear families irrespective of family income were most satisfied with these 24 Mantra organic products.

The concept of customer happiness is complex and encompasses certain factors which affect the level of satisfaction attained by the consumer. Generally, consumer satisfaction is measured using various metrics like Consumer Satisfaction Score (CSAT), Net Promoter Score (NPS), Customer Effort Score, Direct Feedback (In App Customer Surveys, Post Customer Surveys, Customer Surveys Via Email, Volunteered Feedback, Survey Best Practices), Indirect Feedback and Customer Satisfaction (Analytics, Channel Diversification). In this present study, the metric of net promoter score is adopted to calculate the customer satisfaction which is obtained by subtracting the percentage of detractors from that of promoters. It is analyzed by the higher scores, the better. The Net Promoter Score for this study is calculated as under:

Query: How likely would you recommend the products of 24 Mantra Organic?

Never 1	Seldom 2	Sometimes 3	Often 4	Almost Always 5
Responses 4	0	9	22	15
Net Promoter Score (NPS) => (15+22) - (4-0) = 33				

CONCLUSION

Based on the questionnaire served to the respondents, it can be concluded that consumers are most aware of the brand by considering them as necessary products thinking the consumption of organic products helps in contributing to a healthier environment agreeing that the products offered by this brand value for money in terms of quality, met their expectations by purchasing them occasionally mostly through e-commerce websites and rated this brand 4 out of 5. The aspect of the product that consumers were most satisfied with was our quality, health and nutrition, preference for taste, lifestyle changes and reasonable price. Demand for organic foods in India is growing rapidly due to its benefits. In addition, the growing popularity of organic products has significantly expanded the range of organic foods available in retail stores in recent years. Therefore, organic foods will be readily available and the market

will grow tremendously. Nevertheless, the organic food market needs to be organized and strengthened for both producers and retailers. Therefore, the organic food industry can grow significantly over approaching years. The industry is still immature, in an emerging stage, has huge growth potential and can even contribute to the country's economic growth in the long run.

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